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POVERTY: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN INDIA ASPECT

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Abstract:

As a result of "GLOBALIZATION", the "Earth" turns into a small village. Moreover, this is needless to say that the news of a small village is made known to all in a moment. As an instance, the number of the poor and the unemployed persons is more than solvent and employed persons. In one side the image of increasing population and on the other side the unequal distribution excepting the difference between poor and solvent person increase the agony of poor and unemployed person. Once upon a time ,in a specific region, the trouble of the poor and unemployed thrust them to go another region in order to be free from economic hardships and to get more comfortable life otherwise they fell into death due to starvation . At present times, in our India, the people being in unequal and imperfect rivalry are deviated from the right path. To get relief from the trouble , the equal distribution of resources and the awareness of maximum people as well as the same awareness on the part of our every government of our world are vitally necessary to do the needful action taken up to rise from global problems - poverty and unemployment .

India including our state i.e. West Bengal is not outside the problem. In all areas of government and non government sectors the output of surplus employment and shortage employment is carried forward, as the folk is trained for needed courses whereas some or a large number forsake the unnecessary courses. In one side, because of increasing population the food crisis and money crisis take place all over the whole world as well as the number of unemployment and incapable workers is rapidly increasing. From the small industry to hospital, insurance company, transport sector (i.e. air, naval, rail departments) etc. workers are curtailed in a profuse number.

Introduction:

Folk is undergoing, in recent era an economic and social crisis unexampled scale leading to the rapid poverty of the large sector of the world population. National economics as well as international economics are collapsing and unemployment is unprevented. The worlds are suffered from human poverty and unemployment with the destruction of the natural environment. It originates social separation, encourages racism and ethnic enmity, violence of women and often precipitates states as well as countries into destructive between nationalities.

In 1987, 100000 people gathered on the human rights liberties plaza at the Trocadera to honor victims of poverty, hunger, valance and fear. According to jospesh wresinski (1917-1988) founder of ATD Forth world –“where ever men and women condemned to live in extreme poverty, human rights are violated. To come together to ensure that these rights be respected is our solemn duty. “In every year the International day for the eradication of poverty is celebrated on October 17 throughout the world. It was officially recognized by the United Nations in 1992.

The state run national commission for enterprises in the unorganized sector [NCEUS] said most of those living on bellow 20 rupees [half of a dollar] per day were from the informal labor sector with no job or social security, living in abject poverty.

In recent situation all of this report recommends the government provide social security benefit such as maternity and medical expenses as well as pensions to people working in the unorganized sector.

Objective:

To aware the people from poverty and also to know about the recent situation.

Methodology:

At first I have collected the data from journal, gadget, book, internet, newspaper. Then, I have scientifically analyzed and interpret it.

Analysis:

Analysis of social aspects of poverty links conditions of scarcity to aspects of the distribution of resources and power in a society recognizes that poverty may be function of the diminished “capability” of people to live the kinds of lives they value.

Method Of Measuring Poverty:

The methods for measuring poverty in the several countries varies from one country to another. Since its 1990 World Development Report, the World Bank’s “global” poverty measures have mainly based on an International poverty line of about \$1 a day; more precisely, the line \$32.74 per month., at 1993 international purchasing power parity. Now a days it is increased and to gauge sensitively this value \$72.48.

Causes Of Poverty:

The World Banks “voices of the poor” based on research with over 20000 people in 23 countries, identifies a range of factors which poor people identify as part of poverty. These include: precarious livelihoods, excluded locations, physical limitations, gender relationship, lake of security, abuse by those in power, disempowering institutions, limited capabilities, and weak community organizations.

FIGURE-1: MAP SHOWING POVERTY STATUS OF INDIA

Causes Of Poverty In India:

1. Caste system
2. British era
3. India's economic policies

India had started out in the 1950s with:	But ended the 1980s with:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ high growth rates ➤ openness to trade and investment ➤ a promotional state ➤ social expenditure awareness ➤ macro stability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ low growth rates (Hindu rate of growth) ➤ closure to trade and investment ➤ a license-obsessed, restrictive state (License Raj) ➤ inability to sustain social expenditures ➤ Macro instability, indeed crisis. ➤ Poverty has decreased significantly since reforms were started in the 1980s.

Also:

- Over-reliance on agriculture: There is a surplus of labor in agriculture. Farmers are a large vote bank and use their votes to resist reallocation of land for higher-income industrial projects. High population growth rate, although demographers generally agree that this is a symptom rather than cause of poverty. Despite this, India currently adds 40 million people to its middle class every year.
- Neo-liberal policies and their effects

In summary, the official poverty rates in India recorded by National Sample Survey are

Year	Poverty Rate (%)	Poverty Reduction per year(%)
1977-78	51.3	
1983	44.5	1.3
1987-88	38.9	1.2
1993-94	36.0	0.5
1999-2000	(26.09)	not comparable
2004-2005	27.5	0.8

FIGURE-2: Poverty (%) In India From 1977-78 To 2004-05.

Figure-3: Poverty Reductionper Year (%) In India From 1977-78 To 2004-05

Classification Of Poverty:

There are different types of poverty, e.g.

- 1. Absolute poverty:** The World Bank defines extreme poverty as living on less than U.S \$1.25(PPP)/day.
- 2. Moderate poverty:** Which PPP/day is less than \$2 a day?
- 3. Relative poverty:** It views poverty as socially defined and dependent on social context, hence relative poverty is a measure of inequality.
- 4. Ultra poverty:** A term apparently coined by Michel Lipton, connotes being amongst poorest of the poor in low income countries. Lipton defined Ultra poverty as receiving less than 80% minimum caloric intake whilst spending more than 80% of income in food.
- 5. Voluntary poverty:** Among some individuals, such as ascetics, poverty is considered a necessary or desirable condition, which embraced in order to reach certain spiritual, moral, or intellectual states.

How To Reduce Poverty:

We all know about “poverty reduction strategies”. There are follows –

Population reduction: In the mind of certain Central Planners, poverty reduction has almost become synonymous with population reduction.

Economic growth: Historically, poverty has been largely a result of “economic growth”. In 1820, 75% of humanity lived on less than a dollar, while in 2001, only about 20% do. It is possible due to following factors-

- Industrial revolution.
- Green revolution.

Economic liberalization: the World Bank concludes increasing land rights is ‘the key to reducing poverty’ citing that land rights greatly increase poor people’s wealth, in some cases doubling it. In china and India, noted reduction in poverty in recent decades.

Capital, infrastructure and technology: Investments in human capital, in the form of health, is needed for economic growth. Human capital, in the form of education, is an even more important determinant of economic growth than physical capital.

UN economists argue that good infrastructure and technology, such as roads and information networks i.e. computers, mobiles, internet electric equipments, helps market reforms to work.

Aid: Aid in its simplest form is a basic income grant, a form of social security periodically providing citizens with money. The many Govt. take some pilot project like as rewarded to poor student, full free of tuition fees , economically support, conditional cash , transfers, house Building, food supply etc.

Aid from non-governmental organizations may be more effective than governmental aid; this may be because it is better at reaching the poor and better controlled at the grassroots level.

God institution: the “United Nations development program” published a report in April 2000 which focused on good governance in poor countries as a key to economic development and overcoming the selfish interests of wealthy elites often behind state actions in developing nations.

Empowering women: It has helped some countries and sustains economic development & they are more successful in bringing down rapid population growth because they have more said in family planning.

Conclusion:

In modern world, a newly political environment is built up among the countries. They are destroying the whole world by the unequal competition of socio economic activities. We can't evaluate the human resources without properly using human resources which is the main component of the poverty and unemployment.

From the above discussion, it is clear that devaluations are taking place in social and economic areas. With increasing population, plenty of food, clothes and habitation are becoming scarcer and due this effect, poverty and unemployment are increasing. Poverty is such things using by which the politician dream to win in vote. It is applicable in districts as well as in the countries- everywhere the situation is the same. Keeping the problem as political weapons, every politician is busy in pocketing benefits using it. For this reason, terrorist, human-bombers, unsocial activities are being created. As a result, the world now is in target by the terrorists.

Suggestion:

Political leaders should understand that the poverty can be reduced by developments of all the economics sectors (i.e. primary, secondary, tertiary etc.). They only need govt. power. As a result, they take decision either against agriculture or industrialization which is required time to time for vote bank. In fact these activities are causing more poverty and unemployment. In 2009, the world economy fell down due to developed countries policies. The no. of poor people and unemployed persons were increased in states as well as countries. So this year can called as a year of cutting employees. However the government take economic policies that can be solve the above problem.

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